

SYNTHESIS AND CHARACTERIZATION OF A NEW HIGH TEMPERATURE SHAPE MEMORY POLYIMIDE

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ABSTRACT

High temperature shape memory polymers (SMPs) have wide potential applications in various fields, and glass transition temperature (T_g) is a crucial factors in determining their potential applications. Here we report a kind of new shape memory polyimide with a high glass transition temperature (T_g) of 316 °C. The polyimide possesses thermal stable but flexible linkages within the backbone, and the number average molecular weight is 61.5 kg mol⁻¹. The tensile storage modulus of the polyimide decreases slowly with the increase of temperature at glass state, and a sharp glass-rubber transition is observed with a plateau at rubbery state. The storage modulus at 50 °C, 260 °C and 340 °C are 2.3 GPa, 1.3 GPa and 10.1 MPa, respectively. The polymer possesses high thermal stability with the decomposition temperature of 519 °C, and the pyrolysis left 56 % carbonaceous char from the aromatic group at 700 °C. The sample shows nice shape memory properties with a strain recovery rate of 96.1 % and a strain fixing rate of 97.2 %. The mechanism of high temperature shape memory effect of polyimide is proposed, which will stimulate further research on high temperature SMPs.

1 INTRODUCTION

Shape memory polymers (SMPs) have attracted much attention from various fields that require light weight and large recoverable strains.^[1-3] The bulk of the research to date has been concentrated on SMPs with relatively low to medium shape transition temperature for applications in biomedical and surgical materials, smart fabrics, temperatures sensors, actuators, and so on.^[4-6] High temperature SMPs have wide potential applications in severe conditions that undergo high temperatures, such as deployable space structures, shape morphing structures, smart jet propulsion system, high temperature sensors and actuators.^[7-9]

Glass transition temperature (T_g) is usually taken as the shape transition temperature for high temperature SMPs, and T_g of the SMP should be higher than the environmental temperatures to ensure that shape recovery process will not be prematurely triggered by the environment.^[10] Therefore, SMPs with different controllable T_g are required to fulfill the demands of different environments. There have been several reports about high temperature SMPs in recent years, such as thermoset polyaspartimide, thermoplastic and thermoset polyimide and thermoset cyanate.^[10-15] The reported highest T_g of 288 °C is observed in thermoplastic shape memory sulfonated poly(ether ether ketone) ionomers, but the maximum temperature for processing and shape memory design was limited by the desulfonation of the ionomers, which occurred above 300 °C.^[15]

Aromatic polyimide (PI) possesses excellent properties such as high T_g , high thermal stability, high tensile strength and excellent radiation shielding capability, which make them attractive materials for aerospace, electronics and automobiles.^[16-18] Therefore, shape memory polyimide that combines the shape memory effects with the unusual properties of PI are expected to extend applications in many fields. Here we present a series of shape memory polyimide possessing adjustable T_g over 300 °C, high thermal stability and excellent shape memory properties.

The shape memory polyimides here are obtained by polycondensation of 4,4'-(hexafluoroisopropylidene) diphthalic anhydride (6FDA) and 4,4'-diaminodiphenyl ether (ODA), and the hexafluoroisopropylidene and ether linkages within the backbone make the polyimide chains suitable for the reversible phase of shape memory process. The relative flexibility mainly accounts for the T_g higher than those of the previously reported SMPs. By analyzing the relationships between chemical structures and physical properties, the possible mechanism of high temperature shape memory effect of polyimide based on chain flexibility and molecular weight is proposed.

2 EXPERIMENTAL SECTION

Synthesis of the shape memory polyimide. 6FDA (99 %) and ODA (98 %) are purchased from Sigma-Aldrich Co., and the chemicals are used as received. Dimethylacetamide (DMAc) is purchased from Kemiou Chemical Reagent Co. Ltd. and distilled with activated 4 Å molecular sieves under reduced pressure. All the lab instruments and glasswares for the synthesis must be strictly dry.

The shape memory polyimide is synthesized by polycondensation of 6FDA and ODA, and the schematic illustration for the process is shown in Figure 1. 4 m mol ODA and 20 ml DMAc are added to a three-necked flask and then stirred under dry nitrogen for 25 mins. 4 m mol 6FDA is fed into the flask in batches within 1 hr, and intense mechanical stirring is executed at room temperature for 20 hr to form highly viscous PAA. The flask is transferred into a vacuum drying chamber and heated under vacuum at 50 °C for 3 hr to remove the bubbles. The PAA is poured on the glass plate and undergoes a step-wise imidization curing process at 80 °C/2 hr, 120 °C/2 hr, 170 °C/2 hr, 200 °C/2 hr, 260 °C/1 hr, 300 °C/1 hr, and 330 °C/1 hr. The polyimide samples are detached away from glass in deionized water, and was heated at 180 °C for 3 hr to remove the water.

Figure 1. Schematic of polycondensation of the shape memory polyimide.

Molecular weight and structure characterization. The molecular weight of the polyimide samples were determined by size exclusion chromatography (SEC) using Waters 2414 equipped with a refractive index detector in a mixture of N-methyl-2-pyrrolidone (NMP) and 0.05 M lithium bromide at 60 °C. The structure of the shape memory polyimide is studied by Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy (FTIR) on Thermo Nicolet Nexus 870.

Thermomechanical characterization. The storage modulus and loss factor of the specimens versus temperature are characterized by DMA on Netzsch Q800. The samples are cut into rectangular slabs with dimensions of 36 mm× 3 mm× 0.12 mm, and DMA tests were conducted in tensile mode at the frequency of 1 Hz with a heating rate of 3 °C/min. Two tests were conducted for per material with each exhibiting the consistent results, and the measured peak of tan δ curve is used as T_g .

Thermal measurement. The thermal stability of the polyimide was performed by TGA under N₂ environment on a *Mettler-Toledo TGA/DSC instrument* at a heating rate of 10 °C/min.

Shape fixity and recovery measurement. Shape memory cycles to assess shape fixity and recovery are measured using the controlled force mode on TA INSTRUMENT Q800. The procedure for the cyclic tensile tests includes the following steps: (a) heating a sample to T_g+40 °C at 10 °C/min, (b) applying a force that would elongate the sample; (c) reducing the temperature to T_g-120 °C at 10 °C/min, (d) force removal, (e) heating at 10 °C /min to T_g+40 °C. Once recovery of the sample reached a constant value the cycle was repeated by applying the same force used in step (b).

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Molecular weight and structure. The shape memory polyimide is semi-transparent, and it can be dissolved in N-methyl-pyrrolidone (NMP), but it cannot be dissolved in dimethylformamide (DMF), DMAc, tetrahydrofuran (THF) or chloroform. The polyimide possesses number average molecular weight (M_n) of 61.5 kg/mol and weight average molecular weight (M_w) of 110.9 kg/mol.

The structure of the polyimide is characterized with Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy (FTIR), and the FTIR spectra is shown in Figure 2. The peaks at 1785 (C=O, asymmetric stretching) and 1720 cm⁻¹ (C=O, symmetric stretching) are the typical frequencies of imides. Besides, the C-N-C absorption at 1371 (stretching vibration) and 727 cm⁻¹ (bending vibration) also confirm the formation of imides. However, the absorption peak attributed to N-H and O-H (-COOH) bonds does not appear. There is no evidence of carbonyl absorbance in the range 1795-1820 cm⁻¹ and 921-934 cm⁻¹, characteristic of isoimides. The carbonyl stretching frequency in an inter-molecular imide linkage near 1670 cm⁻¹ is not observed, either.^[19] The results demonstrated that the sample is fully imidized within the detection limit of IR.

Figure 2. FTIR of the shape memory polyimide, and regions without peak is cut for clarity.

Thermomechanical properties. The thermomechanical properties of the samples are analyzed with dynamic mechanical analysis (DMA), and the tensile storage modulus (E') of the thermoplastic shape memory polyimide samples versus temperature are shown in Figure 3a. It is seen that E'

decreases slowly with the increase of temperatures in the glassy state, but there is a sharp drops of magnitude in the vicinity of softening point of the polyimide. E' at 50 °C, 260 °C and 340 °C are 2.3 GPa, 1.3 GPa and 10.1 MPa, respectively. The large difference of E' in different states is necessary for the polymer to exhibit shape memory effects. As the temperature gets higher, there is a plateau in the rubbery state, implying that the physical crosslinks are mainly formed by chain entanglements.^[20]

DMA is an effective and sensitive method to determine T_g of polymers with rigid molecular chains, and here T_g of the shape memory polyimide sample is obtained with DMA. The loss factor ($\tan \delta$) versus temperature of the shape memory polyimide is shown in Figure 3b, and the sample shows T_g of 316 °C.

Figure 3.(a) Tensile storage modulus and (b) Loss factor of the shape memory polyimide.

Thermal stability. The thermal stability of the thermoplastic shape memory polyimides are examined with thermal gravimetric analysis (TGA), and the weight loss are shown in Figure 4. The weight loss of 5 % is taken as the effective decomposition temperature (T_d), and T_d of the sample is 519 °C. The pyrolysis left 56 % carbonaceous char from the aromatic group at 700 °C, which means that the shape memory polyimide sample is highly thermal stable.

Figure 4. TGA spectra of shape memory polyimide.

Shape memory performances. Shape recovery (R_r) is the ability of the materials to recover to its original shape, and shape fixity (R_f) is the ability of the switching segments to hold the applied mechanical deformation during this process, and they are two important factors in determining the shape memory effects of SMP. R_r is calculated using Equation 1.

$$R_r(N) = \frac{\varepsilon_m(N) - \varepsilon_p(N)}{\varepsilon_m(N) - \varepsilon_p(N-1)} \times 100 \% \quad 1$$

Here ε_m , ε_p and N denote the strain after the stretching step (before cooling), the strain after recovery, and the cycle number, respectively. R_f is calculated using Equation 2.

$$R_f(N) = \frac{\varepsilon_u(N)}{\varepsilon_m(N)} \times 100 \% \quad 2$$

where ε_u denote the strain in the fixed temporary shape. R_r and R_f are characterized with consecutive shape memory cycles, and the cycles of TP0 are shown in Figure 5. It is observed that R_f are 97.1 %, 97.2 % and 97.1 %, respectively, which are consistent from one cycle to another. R_r was 85.6 % for the first cycle, 96.1 % and 96.6 % for the second and third cycles. The difference in R_r between the first and the following cycles is generally attributed to residual strain resulting from the processing history of the sample.^[21]

Figure 5. The two-dimensional demonstration of changes in strain, stress and temperature with time in stress-controlled consecutive tensile shape memory processes of the shape memory polyimide.

As the reproducibility of R_f and R_r for each sample is good, the values of the second cycle are employed as the shape memory parameters for the samples. The high R_f and R_r of the shape memory polyimide mainly originate from the high modulus below T_g and excellent rubber elasticity above T_g , which cause a sharp decrease in storage modulus from glassy to rubbery state. The high storage modulus is due to the potential elasticity in glassy state, and the low value is due to the entropy elasticity caused by the micro-Brownian movement in rubbery state. The well-defined rubbery plateau is important in the recycle thermal processing of the material, where stable thermal-mechanical properties are required.

Mechanism of the shape memory effects of polyimide. The shape memory effect of SMP is generally explained by dual-state mechanism, in which the molecular chains are regarded as the reversible phase, and the nodes of macromolecule segments attributed to physical or chemical crosslinks are regarded as the permanent phase.^[1,22] The shape memory behavior of polyimide is schematically illustrated in Figure 6, where R_f is 100% if $\Delta L = \Delta L'$ and R_r is 100% if $L_0 = L_0'$.

Figure 6. Shape memory behavior of the polyimide with T_g as shape recovery temperature.

SMPs with low to medium shape transition temperature ($T_g < 110$ °C) are mainly composed of polymers with flexible main chains, while SMPs with high T_g based on polyaspartimide, polyimide, cyanate and PEEK ionomers are all characteristic of the rigid chains comprising phenyl rings and

flexible linkages.^[20, 21, 22] The shape memory polyimide in the current research is obtained by polycondensation of 6FDA/ODA, where the hexafluoroisopropylidene and ether linkage within the backbone provide some flexibility to the highly aromatic polyimide structures, and the molecular chains act as reversible phase. With stoichiometric ratio of dianhydride and diamine, the shape memory polyimide based on 4,4'-oxydiphthalic dianhydride (ODPA)/ODA, 6FDA/1,3-bis(3-aminophenoxy)benzene (BAB) and bis phenol A dianhydride (BPADA)/2,2-bis[4-4(-aminophenoxy)phenyl] propane (BAPP) exhibited T_g of 260.7 °C, 222 °C and 212 °C, respectively,^[11, 12] while the sample based on 6FDA and ODA here show T_g of 316 °C. For dianhydrides, ODPA possess one ether linkage, BPADA possesses one isopropylidene and two ether linkages, while 6FDA possesses one hexafluoroisopropylidene in the backbone. For diamines, BAPP possesses an isopropylidene and two ether linkages, BAB possesses two ether linkages, and ODA possesses one ether linkage in the backbone. There is an obvious increase of flexibility of the rigid polyimide chains following the sequence of BPADA/BAPP>6FDA/BAB> ODPA/ODA>6FDA/ODA. The relative flexibility of the polymer backbone can affect dynamics through the glass transition,^[22] and the polyimide of 6FDA/ODA accordingly exhibit T_g higher than previously reported ones.

4 CONCLUSIONS

In summary, this research provide SMP candidates for high temperature applications. The aromatic polyimide chains possessing thermal stable but flexible units within the backbone can act as the reversible phase for high temperature shape memory effect, and the relative flexibility have great influence on T_g . The shape memory polyimide shows T_g of 316 °C and excellent shape memory performances. This paper has offered some useful approaches to obtain high temperature SMPs with desired T_g , thermomechanical and shape memory properties by tailoring chemical structures. The mechanism of high temperature shape memory effects of polyimide is suggested, and further research on high temperature shape memory polymers will be stimulated.

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